
The influence of the work environment and work motivation on the performance of agricultural training center employees Ministry of Agriculture of the Republic of Indonesia

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ARTICLE INFORMATION	ABSTRACT
<p>Article History: Received: July 03, 2024 Revised: November 11, 2024 Accepted: November 20, 2024 Published: December 13, 2024</p> <p>Keywords: Work Environment, Work Motivation, Employee Performance</p> <p>*Corresponding Author: rafidhia23@gmail.com</p> <p>DOI:</p>	<p>This study examines the impact of the work environment and motivation on employee performance at the Agricultural Training Center, run by the Agricultural Extension and Human Resources Development Agency of the Ministry of Agriculture in Indonesia. An associative quantitative technique was used to investigate the correlations between these factors, using data obtained from 37 workers by questionnaire. The findings show that both the work environment and motivation substantially and positively affect employee performance. Specifically, the work environment and motivation each showed t-values exceeding critical thresholds, with a combined F-value that supports a substantial impact on performance. The implications suggest that organizations can enhance employee performance by improving the work environment and strengthening motivational practices. It is recommended that management continue to foster a supportive work environment and implement strategies to maintain high employee motivation, such as providing recognition, incentives, and opportunities for career development. Further research could include a larger, more diverse sample to validate the findings and explore other factors influencing employee performance.</p>

INTRODUCTION

Human resources (HR) are valuable assets because they help other resources succeed and operate efficiently. Employees, in particular, devote their abilities, energy, time, and creativity to achieving company objectives, therefore this is critical. Ensuring excellent human resources is critical for companies, including the Agricultural Education and Training Center.

The Republic of Indonesia's Ministry of agricultural (Kementan RI) supervises the agricultural, plantation, and livestock sectors, which are managed by a Minister of Agriculture. Performance, defined as the amount and quality of activities accomplished by individuals based on their abilities, expertise, and dedication to organizational duties, is critical. Initial observations indicate that personnel at the Agricultural Education and Training Center perform below expectations.

Initial observations of employee performance at the Agricultural Education and Training Center highlight the need for improved working environmental conditions. Factors such as uncontrolled temperatures, lack of adequate ventilation, and high noise levels may be the primary causes of the observed substandard performance. Apart from that, the lack of adequate work facilities can also affect employee productivity and welfare. Providing an optimal working environment at the Agricultural Education and Training Center will not only improve

performance, but also create more positive conditions for all team members to develop professionally and personally.

A positive work atmosphere at the Agricultural Education and Training Center will provide employees a sense of security, which can boost their drive to perform more successfully and productively. High motivation is also required to generate passion for attaining corporate goals, in accordance with the work culture in place and the degree of expertise exhibited by each worker. Thus, boosting the quality of the work environment and employee motivation at the Agricultural Education and Training Center will be critical to increasing performance and attaining organizational goals more effectively.

Apart from environmental and motivational factors, organizational culture and competence also impact performance. Organizational culture shapes employee adaptation, problem-solving abilities, and integration within the organization. Competency, which involves knowledge, skills, and attitudes, determines an individual's proficiency and strength in carrying out tasks.

Thus, researchers are interested in investigating and examining these factors because they believe that improving the quality of the work environment, employee motivation, organizational culture, and individual competence will be the primary drivers in improving the performance. It is intended that this would not only enhance organizational goals, but also provide the groundwork for long-term growth and development in Indonesia's agricultural, plantation, and livestock industries.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Performance

(Stephen P. Robbins, 2024) defines performance as the results achieved by employees in their work, measured based on certain criteria that are relevant to their work role. (Afandi, 2018) characterizes performance as the results achieved by individuals/groups in an organization, within the scope of their authority and responsibility, which aim to achieve organizational goals in a legal and ethical manner. (M. Kaswan, 2019) describes employee performance as a manifestation of their behavior in the workplace, where they apply skills, competencies and knowledge that contribute value to the organization. (Edy Sutrisno, 2019) stated that employee performance includes work results that can be seen in terms of quality, quantity, working hours and cooperation towards achieving organizational goals. (Anwar Prabu Mangkunegara, 2020) defines performance as the qualitative and quantitative results of the tasks carried out by an employee in line with the responsibilities delegated to him. (Anwar Prabu Mangkunegara, 2017) also describes performance dimensions and indicators, which include work quality, quantity and efficiency in time management, performance behavior such as initiative and thoroughness, as well as personal traits such as leadership, honesty and creativity.

Work Environment

(Schultz & Sydney, 2020) define the work environment as conditions in the workplace that influence employee behavior and attitudes. (Hasibuan, 2020) characterizes it as a condition or environment that can affect employee performance, health, safety and welfare, which includes physical, social and psychological factors. (Sedarmayanti, 2018) describes the work environment as consisting of tools, materials, physical environment, work methods and settings, both individual and group. (Nitisemito, 2019) states that the work environment includes all elements around employees that can influence their work, such as the availability of air conditioning and lighting. (Sedarmayanti, 2018) further categorizes work environment dimensions and indicators into physical factors such as lighting, temperature, air quality, noise level, and decoration, and

non-physical factors including interpersonal relationships between co-workers and hierarchical relationships between superiors and subordinates, as well as collaboration between employees.

Work Motivation

(Luthans, 2021) describes work motivation as a process that shapes how individuals direct, intensify and maintain their efforts to achieve certain goals at work. (Gary Dessler., 2023) defines it as a driving force that motivates individuals to strive to achieve organizational goals, as long as these goals are aligned with their personal needs. (Griffin, 2022) characterizes work motivation as the complex process underlying why individuals engage in certain behaviors in the context of their work, highlighting its dependence on factors such as individual needs, values, goals and expectations. (Maruli Tua Sitorus, 2020) emphasized that work motivation includes everything that originates from individual desires, which fuel enthusiasm and encouragement to influence, guide and support behavior aimed at achieving work-related goals or desires. Dimensions and indicators of motivation in this research, according to (Rivai et al., 2016), includes: the need for achievement, including developing creativity, improving skills, and working effectively; need for affiliation, which involves fostering good interpersonal relationships and encouraging collaboration; and the need for power, which includes the desire to exert influence, assume responsibility, lead, and compete.

METHOD

All steps needed to plan and carry out research are included in research design, according to (Silaen, 2018). Associative research aims to explain, predict and control phenomena. (Sugiyono, 2023) explains that population is all objects or subjects that researchers decide to study with certain characteristics. This research involved 37 employees; Sugiyono stated that the sample was chosen to represent the population as a whole. Because the population was less than 100, 37 respondents from the population were taken as samples. In this research, the data analysis method used is multiple linear regression, which was carried out using the SPSS computer program, in accordance with the associative hypothesis approach used in this research.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1. Coefficient of Determination Test Results
Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.743 ^a	.552	.526	2.330	1.849

a. Predictors: (Constant), Motivasi Kerja, Lingkungan

b. Dependent Variable: Kinerja Pegawai

Source : SPSS Program Output

Based on the data in the table above, the work environment and motivation determine 55% of employee performance. Organizational culture, competencies, and other characteristics not covered in this research account for the remaining 45%.

**Table 2. t Test Results
Coefficients^a**

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	6.694	4.476		1.495	.144
1 Lingkungan	.420	.200	.371	2.101	.043
Motivasi Kerja	.399	.168	.421	2.380	.023

a. Dependent Variable: Kinerja Pegawai

Source : SPSS Program Output

According to the t test results, the calculated t values for Environmental factors (2.101) and Work Motivation (2.380) both exceed the critical t table value of 2.03. Additionally, the significance values (sig.) for these variables are 0.043 and 0.023, respectively, which are both below the accepted significance threshold of 0.05. This indicates that the null hypothesis (Ho) is rejected, and the alternative hypothesis (Ha) is accepted for both variables. Therefore, it can be concluded that both the work environment and motivation have a strong and positive impact on employee performance at the Agricultural Education and Training Center of the Ministry of Agriculture of the Republic of Indonesia.

**Table 3. F Test Result
ANOVA^a**

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	227.500	2	113.750	20.950	.000 ^b
1 Residual	184.608	34	5.430		
Total	412.108	36			

a. Dependent Variable: Kinerja Pegawai

b. Predictors: (Constant), Motivasi Kerja, Lingkungan

Source: SPSS Program Output

Based on the results of the F test, the Fcount value of 20.950 was higher than the Ftable value of 3.28. Additionally, the significance value (sig.) was 0.000, which is below the typical significance threshold of 0.05. This indicates that the null hypothesis (Ho) is rejected, and the alternative hypothesis (Ha) is accepted. In conclusion, these findings suggest that the combination of the work environment and motivation positively and significantly affects the performance of employees at the Agricultural Education and Training Center of the Indonesian Ministry of Agriculture.

DISCUSSION

The results of this study align with previous research highlighting the significant role of the work environment in enhancing employee performance. As noted by Demaz Adithya Widharma (2021), a positive and supportive work environment greatly impacts employee performance. This study reaffirms the idea that employees are more likely to excel when working in a conducive environment, as it directly influences their productivity and job satisfaction. The concept that a well-maintained work setting enhances performance is consistent with Widharma's (2021) findings, which stress the importance for organizations to focus on environmental factors to boost overall performance.

Additionally, the research results support the findings of Nunu Nurjaya (2021), who also concluded that the work environment positively and significantly influences employee

performance. Nurjaya's study emphasizes that a conducive work environment fosters better focus and reduces workplace stress, which, in turn, boosts performance. This research adds to the growing body of evidence suggesting that creating an optimal work environment should be a key focus for organizations aiming to improve employee performance and achieve their goals.

The combination of work environment and work motivation also plays a crucial role in enhancing employee performance, as indicated by Rifatun Nadhiyah and Syahirul Alim (2022). Their research demonstrated that both factors when considered together positively influence performance. Similarly, this study found that work environment and motivation work synergistically to produce better outcomes for employees, aligning with Nadhiyah and Alim's (2022) findings. Motivated employees, working in a supportive environment, are more engaged and productive, which ultimately contributes to the organization's success.

In conclusion, this study reinforces the importance of both a positive work environment and high levels of motivation in driving employee performance. These findings are consistent with the works of Demaz Adithya Widharma (2021), Nunu Nurjaya (2021), and Rifatun Nadhiyah and Syahirul Alim (2022), who all emphasize the significant role of these variables in improving organizational outcomes. Organizations should continue to focus on creating a supportive work environment and fostering motivation to enhance employee performance and achieve organizational goals.

CONCLUSION

According to this study, a positive work atmosphere and employee motivation have a considerable impact on staff performance at the Indonesian Ministry of Agriculture's Agricultural Training Center. A happy work atmosphere increases employee productivity, which contributes to organizational success, whereas motivated people are more likely to perform better, which has a direct influence on meeting organizational goals. The findings emphasize the necessity of creating a positive work environment and applying effective motivator tactics to improve performance. However, the study is restricted to a single institution, which may limit the generalizability of the findings. Future study might include a bigger, more varied sample and investigate additional elements, such as leadership styles and organizational culture, to acquire a better understanding of the variables that influence employee performance. Based on the findings, employers should continue to enhance their work environments by assuring safety, good communication, and support, as well as giving motivational possibilities such as recognition, rewards, and career development programs.

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